

From ideologies to practice: A political ecology approach to green transitions— The case of Tanzania’s Ujamaa sustainability communities

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable living is a core construct within the global green movement. Envisioning a more environmentally conscious future for Earth, the green movement denounces high consumption lifestyles and fossil fuel dependence. Like other nations, African countries are increasingly joining the green movement by trying to pursue low-carbon growth and sustainable development. So far, this green transition has been easier said than done. For the most part, capacity gaps and non-compliance among local populations and special interest groups within countries persist for various reasons. Green transitions thus constitute a complex meshwork of ideologies, policies, and practices that need further exploration in the development literature. Whereas previous studies have focused on the econometrics of green transitions, this study takes a political ecology approach. Utilizing a qualitative historical case study and content analysis, this article examines key factors that impact the realization of this proposed green future for the African continent. The historical case analyzed is the Ujamaa policy and communities (Ujamaa Villages) established by the government of Tanzania between 1967 and 1985. The findings of this study suggest that despite the promise of a more just, sustainable, and eco-friendly future, embedded colonial legacies, hypercapitalist markets, and neoliberal values often undermine the implementation of programs and projects that are needed to jump-start and maintain green transitions, particularly in natural resource-dependent post-colonial societies. Shaped by these ideological and socio-ecological paradoxes, government interests, media portrayals, and public choices are often antagonistic to sustainability practices. This article further highlights the intricate interplay between political ideology, development economics, social-environmental movements, and land use ecology in Africa and the wider Global South.

1. Introduction

In recent years, there have been increased efforts to create an alternate future where societies are greener [1,2]. Greening refers to the process of transforming environments, spaces, and lifestyles into a more environmentally friendly version [3]. It is considered a holistic approach to restoring degraded ecosystems, combating desertification, building infrastructure, and promoting sustainable land management practices and economies free from fossil fuels [4]. Sustainability is a guiding principle within the green movement, advocating for living systems that satisfy present needs without jeopardizing the capacity of future generations to fulfill their own needs [5]. Green and sustainability are often used interchangeably in their respective literature because they typically convey similar meanings [6,7]. However, the emergence of the global green movement can be traced back to the mid-20th century as a reaction to heightened environmental consciousness and apprehensions regarding industrial pollution, resource exhaustion, and climate

variations [8,9]. This movement gathered momentum through community-based activism, scientific inquiry, and international accords, notably exemplified by the Stockholm Conference of 1972 [10].

Green transitions are thought to pave the way from the current market-oriented development, which is pegged to fossil fuels and nature exploitation, to a more just and environmentally conscious paradigm of sustainable development [11]. Thereby establishing societies capable of flourishing socially, economically, and ecologically. Like social and economic development, green transformations at the local level take place through programs, projects, and initiatives undertaken by the government and may involve other stakeholders such as industry leaders and civil society groups [12,13]. At a more granular level, sustainable living communities, also referred to as eco-villages, emerged primarily as experimental models promoting balanced ecosystems that jointly center the well-being of people, nature, and the planet [14,15]. Therefore, predicated on environmental soundness, sustainable societies are based on economic practicability, social fairness, and communal living

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or interdependence [16,17].

Sustainable communities are found around the world, mostly in small enclaves. However, for thousands of years, they have been touted as solutions to human-caused environmental challenges and for creating sustainable societal alternatives [18]. Theoretically, sustainable communities can be scaled up to sustainable countries, regions, and beyond. Aiming to prioritize ecological sustainability, their habitats often emphasize the integration of low-carbon renewable energy, organic agriculture, and waste reduction practices [18]. In the African context, the rise and fall of the Ujamaa Villages project (Ujamaas) in Tanzania offers an intriguing historical case study. Implemented between 1967 and 1985, Ujamaas were, in essence, a series of sustainability communities built on a nationwide scale [19,20]. It was an experiment seeking to transform Tanzania from an underdeveloped colonial society to a modern independent nation-state through a rural communal model, which prioritized self-reliance and self-sufficiency. However, Ujamaas experienced varying degrees of success and challenges. The anticipated positive national socioeconomic development outcomes were not realized due to several factors, from resource needs to mismanagement and others [21].

Whereas previous studies emphasize either the politics or economics of green transitions, this study takes a political ecology approach. It draws upon the intellectual traditions of political ecology and conducts a historical analysis and content analysis using historical newspapers and historical policy documents accessed through archival research. Although not often recognized as such in the development literature, Ujamaa significantly transformed the environment and rural and urban ecosystems of Tanzania in a relatively short time. In the context of green transitions, the ideology-practice nexus explores how environmental values and beliefs shape practical actions toward sustainability. Ideology, in this sense, refers to the underlying principles and motivations driving green transitions, such as ecological stewardship, social justice, and economic resilience [22,23]. Meanwhile, praxis (putting ideological principles into practice) involves the concrete actions and policies implemented to achieve these goals, like renewable energy adoption and waste reduction [24,25]. The nexus, therefore, examines how aligning ideology with practice ensures that environmental goals are effectively pursued [26]. Discrepancies between ideology and practice can lead to ineffective or contradictory outcomes, making it crucial to integrate values with actionable strategies for successful green transitions [27].

Tanzania is a country (or nation-state) carved out by European colonial action. While Tanzania is an African nation, its progress and development as a modern (or post-modern) nation-state have been domestically and internationally measured by Western metrics and standards, which have been mostly politically liberal and economically capitalist, [28,29]. Furthermore, since gaining independence in 1961, Tanzanian electors, like many former colonial states and countries worldwide, have voted into office successive leaders and administrations on the basis that they could deliver these, all be it, Western development standards [30–32]. Additionally, these standards and aspirations of modern development were determined based on the nation's membership in and signatory to agreements set through intergovernmental organizations such as the World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), and the World Trade Organization (WTO) [33,34]. The nation operates in an international system designed by Western hegemony and maintained through a set of long-curated beliefs and values that historically have reinforced Western primacy and those nations that aspire to mainly Western norms [35,36].

Ujamaa policies and the associated practice of building Ujamaa communities across Tanzania's countryside was an early attempt by an African post-colonial society to implement a large-scale alternative development model that had sustainability principles at its core. An analysis of Ujamaa's associated policies and outcomes—be they perceived as successes or failures—can, therefore, provide insights into

the intricacies likely to be involved in the present-day and future implementation of alternative sustainability projects in Africa and the wider Global South. This is largely due to these states' natural resource dependency and political-economic position in the world system. In most African developing countries, green transformations (and approaches to sustainability) are found to be heavily informed by 'alternative' ideologies such as egalitarianism, socialism, and inclusivity (at least in theory). This is due to post-independent era efforts to counter colonial legacies and subsequent neoliberal emergence in those states. However, from a political ecology perspective, these alternative ideologies are generally (and sometimes fundamentally) incompatible with the presiding core capitalist logic of supply and demand, private ownership of land, acquisition by dispossession, and profit by labor exploitation. These contradictions upset the status quo and are shown to engender negative criticism from mainstream media and influence the public (and special interest groups) away from complying with, supporting, or choosing sustainability alternatives—which are mostly beneficial for the well-being of people and the environment in the long term. Moreover, the associated practice of sustainability and the design of sustainability systems are often faced with technical, resource, and environmental challenges that undermine the longevity of large-scale sustainability initiatives.

1.1. Tanzania's Ujamaa policy and communities (1967–1985)

Ujamaa was primarily a social and economic policy implemented by the Tanzanian government. It was developed by the nation's founding president, Julius Nyerere, through the 1967 Arusha Declaration. The Declaration underscored the principles of self-reliance, egalitarianism, and socialism within African traditional values (African socialism) [37, 38]. As the nation's seminal socialist manifesto, the declaration's focal tenets were the nationalization of key industries (commanding heights of the economy), land reforms designed to benefit small-scale farmers, and the establishment of cooperative organizations. The aim was to address poverty and inequality and dismantle capitalist economic structures inherited from the colonial era [39]. This was pursued through establishing self-sustaining cooperative communities, Ujamaa Villages, as a way to foster socioeconomic development and social justice. It was primarily inhabited by rural farmers and their families, and then later peri-urban settlers who were moved from Dar es Salaam into the planned formal villages [40].

In addition to its focus on agriculture, Ujamaa brought together rural populations in nucleated settlements, each consisting of around 250 families surrounded by resources to supplement them [39]. This is a form of sustainability design—pooling limited resources in compact formations for service delivery efficiency [41]. Ujamaa communities consisted of neighborhoods created with farming plots nearby for food production and social institutions located in the center. Fig. 4 shows two examples of the physical layout of new rural villages that were developed in the early 1960s by the Tanganyika Rural Settlement Commission [42]. These plans were later adapted and used to construct Ujamaa communities in independent Tanzania. These centralized communities, for the most part, made it easier to distribute agricultural services such as fertilizer and seeds to rural populations. As well as making it less cumbersome to deliver social services such as healthcare and education. For instance, the population in each community had access to a centrally located schoolhouse and clinic.

With wavering levels of success, by the late 1970s, Ujamaa policies had declined. In 1985, it was discontinued when Nyerere stepped down from the presidency. Often missing from the development-related discourse on Ujamaa, which this study highlights, is the recognition that Ujamaa was also an ecological policy informed by sustainability principles. Its focus on self-reliance in food and agriculture, modernizing farming practices, and rural-urban population trans-mobility, among others, underscores its ecological character. Meanwhile, a series of droughts, famines, and resource gaps inflicted substantial challenges to

the implementation of this national socioeconomic development project—highlighting how the policy was shaped by ecological change. The examination of Ujamaa's political ecology dimensions reveals its susceptibilities and triumphs that were defined by the confluence of ecological change, ideology, and political decision-making.

1.2. Ujamaa as an early case of social-environmental transition

The Ujamaa Villages rural development experiment in Tanzania, introduced by Julius Nyerere in the 1960s and 70 s, can be analyzed as an early form of social-environmental transition, even though it predates contemporary conceptualization of what constitutes green (low-carbon) transitions. While the Ujamaa model was not explicitly focused on environmental sustainability as we understand it now, it emphasized communal living, self-reliance, and collective agricultural practices, which had ecological implications. Firstly, in the reorganizing rural communities into cooperative villages, it sought to promote social equity and economic self-sufficiency [43]. The transition from a colony to post-colonial society, and the further process of attempted decolonization which followed in the 1960s to 1980s, caused major social-environmental shifts. Although not often recognized as such, for societies that have experienced significant natural resource exploitation attributed to Western colonization and imperialism, post-colonial socioeconomic development meant restructuring the relationship between people and the environment. This was particularly with land—physically in terms of land use practices, economically in terms of who benefits from the associated commercialization of its natural resources, and legally in terms of access and ownership rights [44]. This is one of the main reasons why equity and justice are increasingly featured in the discourse on green transitions, especially concerning developing countries [45,46].

Secondly, in a post-colonial context, Ujamaa represented an attempt to break free from natural resource exploitative colonial systems to reconstitute a society that had, ideally, a more sustainable relationship with the land [47]. Therefore, although different from the current green transformation, primarily driven by global climate change concerns, Ujamaa can still be understood as part of a broader socio-ecological transition, where social justice, ecological management, and sustainable development intersect [48,49]. Thus, in a sense, both movements reflect responses to structural inequities, though in somewhat different historical and environmental contexts. This was, and in many ways remains, a recurring theme in Tanzania and similar African post-colonial societies today as they respond to climate and environmental challenges that are driving societal transitions towards ecological sustainability, low-carbon economies, and sustainable development [50,51].

Therefore, green transitions in significant ways are similar in scale (or will be) to the major socioeconomic and political transformations (or reforms) that post-colonial societies underwent in their transition from colonies to self-governing nations. Many of those structural conditions, financial constraints, and capability and capacity challenges faced back then remain today in Tanzania, like many former colonial states in the developing world [52,48]. Likewise, these challenges will need to be examined and overcome as green (low-carbon) transitions become commonplace in the global development agenda, especially reducing fossil fuel dependence in the region [53,54]. Based on their social-environmental impacts, deep (de)colonial legacies, socioeconomic development implications, and social justice needs, contemporary green transitions and Ujamaa's post-colonial development transition have fundamental theoretical and practice commonalities from which lessons for present and future transitions can be garnered. Certainly, there is a need for more of such historical analysis that explores these aspects of green transitions in post-colonial societies and across the wider developing world.

2. Theoretical approach

This study is primarily guided by the theories associated with the field of political ecology. Emerging in the 1980s as an interdisciplinary field, political ecology analyzes environmental issues and problems using the concepts and methods of political economy, particularly Marxian political economy [55,56]. Later on, new ideas from post-structural social theory and nonequilibrium ecology were incorporated [57]. Whereas stable ecosystems have long been viewed as being difficult to upset because their regulatory mechanisms are highly effective [58], nonequilibrium ecology is particularly interesting because it departed from the ideal to suggest that ecosystem dynamics are rarely in equilibrium, rather, they are strongly influenced by disturbance, heterogeneity, and multiple stable states [59]. Political shifts have proved to be one of the most destabilizing forces on ecosystems and society (and varied forms of human organization in general) [60,61].

Sustainability and greening are social and environmental movements that have emerged in response to the increasing awareness of the detrimental impact of human activity on global ecology and socioeconomic development, not just the environment [62,63]. They also reflect the increasing recognition that political processes, states, governments, and ideologies have shaped the natural environment and vice versa [64]. Reflecting a more profound realization, these movements signify a shift on a global scale towards a more ecologically sustainable way of life. Intellectually, people and society as a whole are undergoing a transition from a modern industrial worldview to an ecological worldview, one that equates to the postmodern transformation that occurred with philosophy and religion, as well as the social and natural sciences [65]. Political ecology, therefore, examines the intricate ways in which political, economic, and social forces intersect to shape environmental and social systems and their management. This approach or worldview can be used to investigate an array of interconnected things, including the uneven allocation of environmental resources, disputes concerning natural resources, power structures within environmental governance, and the socio-environmental frameworks that mold policies and practices [56,66].

One of the most destabilizing global phenomena (politically or otherwise) in recent human history is colonization and imperialism [67, 68]. Although political ecology as a field of study and theoretical approach emerged out of Western episteme, it is essentially a critique of Western, liberal, and capitalist use of the environment and natural resources. This ties it closely with decolonial thought, as well as notions of traditional communality, which is not only African but comes out of early human history societal evolution. Ujamaa was designed to be both decolonial and traditional but also anti-capitalist and de-liberal. It has been critical of linear development that is natural resource exploitative. Furthermore, political ecology contextualized to non-Western realities opens up a more nuanced discourse. One that recognizes the deeper structural forces that African nations must grapple with in the process of transitioning to green (carbon-neutral) societies [69,70]. For example, examining Tanzania's Ujamaa policies and practices captures more effectively the historical legacies of colonialism that continue to shape social and ecological dynamics in East Africa [21,71]. Especially in an era where sustainable development is the major development paradigm, political ecology speaks to the ongoing paradoxes and resource disparity challenges that nation-states that have historically been at the periphery of global power must additionally navigate to achieve global green transition benchmarks [72,73].

2.1. Political ecology from below

Over the years, there has been an expanding tradition of political ecology from below. This critical political ecology was employed in this study by interrogating the Tanzania case and grappling with issues of environmental justice, dispossession, and decoloniality as remnants of

colonial debts [74,75]. It can also be regarded as a Third World, developing world, or Global South political ecology, as it engages with the historical context of an imbalanced world order. This further acknowledges that post-colonial and contemporary development policies and models originate directly or indirectly, in solidarity with or in opposition to Western hegemony—liberal, colonial, and capitalist—in development theory and practice [76–78].

Furthermore, as decision-makers and development architects envision a more just and sustainable future for Tanzania and wider Africa, they are called upon to weigh the impact of their political decision-making on ecological change more carefully, appreciating it as a critical aspect of green transitions toward sustainable development [79,80]. For example, Tanzania, as an agriculture and natural resource-dependent economy, is more susceptible to climate change [81]. Meanwhile, the nation cannot respond to extreme weather events adequately due to pre-existing structural (mostly socioeconomic) factors [82,83]. Many of these same ecological realities faced the nation during the 1950s to 70 s, such as drought and famine [84]. These environmental realities significantly impacted the viability of deep rural Ujamaa communities and negatively impacted the country's larger socioeconomic development outcomes [85]. The Ujamaa case also sheds light on the importance of local knowledge and community practices that are essential for sustainable resource management [43]. But also explicitly demonstrates that in unreasoning pursuit of autocratically state-determined targets, even local officials and domestically-managed implementation of green transitions can overlook or undervalue important aspects of societal change happening locally [47].

Additionally, the Tanzania Ujamaa case study emphasizes the complexities of local power relations and global power dynamics—a feature often underexamined in discourses at the intersection of socioeconomic development and ecological change. This multi-scale power dynamic (local to regional, to continental, to global) was aimed at formalizing and legitimizing Tanzania's self-determination in a way that affirmed it as a modern state in the international system. All this while rejecting colonial forces still at play domestically and adopting a Socialist ideology that, in due time, was rejected by the local polity, which it was meant to help, as well as being viewed with great suspicion by the liberal Western powers at the heights of the Cold War [86]. Furthermore, political ecology through a particular African lens highlights the interconnectedness of social, economic, and environmental factors in a way that prioritizes social justice, focusing on the unique adaptive strategies that emerged from Ujamaa's emphasis on collective well-being and equality in resistance to colonial exploitation [87,88]. However, it also speaks to contradictions like the injustice that local villagers reportedly endured at the hands of local officials enforcing Ujamaa mandatory relocation orders [89], as well as contemporary discriminatory rural migration issues that recently resurfaced [90].

2.2. A Global South green movement

A Global South green movement would then emphasize sustainable development practices tailored to the unique social, economic, and political contexts of developing countries. As such, social justice and equity are foundational to this movement, addressing issues like land rights and the disproportionate impacts of climate change on marginalized populations [91,92]. Furthermore, unlike mainstream environmental movements, Global South perspectives attempt to prioritize grassroots participation, local knowledge, and decolonization [93,94]. It is an approach that mostly believes that local communities possess valuable insights into sustainable resource management and ecological practices. For example, in recent years, there has been a push to integrate Indigenous knowledge about the environment and ecological change into conservation efforts, as well as to right the wrongs of the past. The

Global South green movement, therefore, seeks to honor indigenous practices that promote sustainability. It focuses on adapting environmental solutions to fit specific local contexts, resisting one-size-fits-all models [95,96]. In some ways, when approached through deep critical lenses, it emphasizes the importance of community agency and actively works against the co-optation of environmental initiatives by powerful interests [97]. In this regard, collaborative networks across borders are also vital, allowing communities to share strategies and support one another in facing similar challenges, oftentimes through traditional forms of governance [98].

Ultimately, this side of the movement strives to align environmental well-being with economic development, prioritizing sustainable livelihoods that benefit communities. In centering the voices and experiences of those most affected by environmental issues, a Global South green movement tries to foster (or at least envision) a holistic, reparatory, and inclusive approach to green transitions and sustainable development [99]. Many of these Global South environmental themes are engaged in this study. Tanzania's Ujamaa experiment itself tried to embody some of these social justice, equity, and decoloniality principles but also demonstrated cooptation and government authority, which acted contradictory to the Arusha's stated goals, encroaching on the rights of the most vulnerable in the society. At the same time, environmental-social challenges of drought, famine, and war wreaked havoc on East Africa, undermining the nation's post-colonial progress. Meanwhile, at the regional and international level, Tanzania faced mounting criticism for its deeper entrenchment of socialist ideologies and state practices by 1970. Especially at the height of the Cold War, in a Liberal-dominated international system, Tanzania was up against the odds. It was also attempting to solicit Foreign Development Aid while simultaneously trying to legitimize its self-determination from the West [100]. Much of these complexities and paradoxes remain today. The global world order has not drastically changed since the end of Tanzania's Ujamaa policy and communities. Neither have Tanzania's local realities of rural poverty and agriculture and resource dependence, [101,102]. In fact, some scholars argue that contemporary challenges have amplified in an era defined by cascading and interlocking crises of climate change, environmental degradation, and widening inequality [28,103]. Developing countries will have to more strategically engage these issues as they attempt to transition to green (carbon-neutral) societies.

Research on political ecology then encompasses a variety of methodological approaches. These include political-economic analysis, multi-scale analysis, historical analysis, ethnography, content analysis, and ecological field studies [104]. Furthermore, other scholars, such as McManus [105], have noted the increased use of political ecology approaches to understand issues such as development, water allocation, deforestation, land management, and others. For these reasons, political ecology was selected as an analytical approach to guide this study. In essence, examining how and why economic structures and power relations drive ecological change in an increasingly interconnected world. This underscores the reality that larger social, economic, and environmental forces are at play whether or not scholars acknowledge them. Roberts [106] For instance, argues that political ecology has a potent tradition for “investigating the practices and impacts of large-scale resource development projects in subsistence-oriented communities in the Global South” (1). The Global South is a term that has come to refer to the collective of low- to middle-income developing countries within the international system [107]. Political ecology research, therefore, has the potential to scrutinize the extent to which global (or globally imposed) political values, ideologies, and global environmental forces shape local realities and vice versa in some cases [49].

Like other theoretical approaches, political ecology has its limitations. As an inherently interdisciplinary field and approach, it grapples with integrating disciplinary interests and influences into a single

rigorous framework [108]. These limitations have become more evident in an epoch defined by a cascading cross-cutting polycrisis, which includes global climate change, pollution, conflict, health and economic disparities, and natural resource depletion. Grounding this study within a fairly renowned historical case study, which can be cross-referenced through various historical literature and reports, strengthens the variability and reliability of its findings. Despite these limitations, political ecology's strong emphasis on applied methods strengthens its rigor [108,109]. This often leads to interesting and thought-provoking perspectives, particularly those on socioeconomic vulnerabilities caused by ecological transformations driven by ideology and political decision-making.

3. Methods and calculations

Drawing parallels with the past and present, the study examines a past event—the Ujamaa Villages—but intends to derive lessons learned regarding the ideology and practice nexus to inform present and future approaches to green transitions in Africa. This study uses mixed methods associated with the field of political ecology. The specific methods used are Qualitative Historical Analysis and Content Analysis. As mentioned, the historical analysis is being conducted on the Ujamaa Villages experiment and its associated policies implemented in Tanzania between 1967 and 1985. The historical analysis focuses on understanding the interests of the government. As well as how and why state policies and political ideologies shaped the ecology of these communities—the rural landscape and the semi- or peri-urban spaces that were dispossessed of people to populate the Ujamaas. Historical analysis can be defined as the critical examination and interpretation of past events, processes, and contexts to understand their significance and implications for the future [110,111]. When conducting qualitative historical analysis, researchers delve into historical records, texts, artifacts, and other primary sources to construct narratives and uncover underlying meanings. Based on its ability to provide rich contextual insights, qualitative historical analysis is highly advantageous. It often allows for nuanced interpretations, enabling researchers to uncover complexities and subtleties overlooked in quantitative analyses [112]. It is equally useful in situations where quantitative data is unavailable, or in this case, not capturing ideological forces that support (or undermine) alternative environmental practices. One main limitation of qualitative historical analysis, however, is the reliance on available sources, which could restrict the scope of inquiry and create bias [113,114]. To address this, in addition to historical newspaper articles, I consulted a variety of policy document sources created when Ujamaa was being implemented. These are policy documents and newspaper articles from three well-known news sources.

As part of conducting the historical case analysis, I carried out a content analysis. The aim of using content analysis in this study was to decipher (1) the Tanzanian government's interests in establishing these communities and their impact on or relationship to ecology and the natural environment and (2) to examine the factors that possibly had a significant impact on the implementation of the Ujamaa policy, particularly (a) the local public's interest and (b) the international media's view (and influence) of all these developments. As a research method, content analysis examines spoken, written, or visual communication to uncover underlying patterns, ideologies, and structures embedded within discourse [115]. There are two approaches to content analysis: conceptual (or summative) analysis and relational (or directed) analysis are the two general approaches to content analysis [116,117]. This paper incorporates both but emphasizes direct analysis. The first stage includes identifying the frequency of keywords that demonstrate the visible aspects of the content—summative analysis [118]. Meanwhile, the second and more substantive stage is exploring meaning in the relations between text and context—directed analysis [119]. In this study, these two stages combine to help with identifying patterns and themes and to further ground the interpretation of the content in the theoretical

framework used—political ecology theory.

3.1. Data sources and software

Three sets of newspaper sources, along with policy documents, were utilized in this study.

For the newspaper sources, one local newspaper—*The Daily News*—and two international newspaper sources—*The Washington Post* and *The New York Times*—were used. Firstly, to examine Tanzania's Ujamaa experiment in the international and historical context in which it was crafted and implemented, I chose to analyze the news content produced by two noteworthy newspapers with a global reach. These newspapers had writers and sections dedicated to international affairs and had a global readership during the period concurrent with the establishment and operation of the Ujamaa Villages and the general social and political atmosphere of Tanzania between 1965 and 1985. More importantly, these two newspaper sources are American and Western in their sociopolitical tradition. The editorial opinions, public discourse, and perspectives of their writers and publishing bureaucrats often reflected the dominant liberal and capitalist ideologies of the global environment in which Tanzania and others were emerging as post-colonial nations [120, 121]. The nation's development and progress, like other post-colonial states, despite attempts to infuse cultural traditions and non-Western features, were—again—being evaluated and engaged with bilaterally and multilaterally through these Western (Global North) norms of development [122–125]. Likewise, the 'rules of the game' or the global geopolitical landscape were already determined and later adopted by Tanzania as it transitioned to independence, joining the international community [126,127].

This is what makes this study a worthwhile contribution (including methodologically) to the literature on the intersection of socioeconomic development, ecological change, and sustainability. It examines through international public discourse the complexity of large-scale development projects and their impacts—on people and the natural environment, and vice versa. Tanzania under the Nyerere administration contradictory, or paradoxically, tried to 'play the game' and benefit from it, but at the same time, tried to reject foreign aid and the dominant Western liberal ideology of development, choosing socialism in its place. This post-colonial transition was a complex process that, in many ways, parallels contemporary conditions as nations now attempt to transition to carbon-neutral societies, rejecting fossil fuel dependence and capitalist growth. It appears a more arduous and stratified or non-linear path towards sustainable development for the Global South's still-developing countries that have historically been at the periphery of global wealth and power compared to their Western (Global North) counterparts who write, control, and dominate the rules of the 'development game.'

Secondly, using *The Washington Post* and *The New York Times* alongside *The Daily News* for analyzing Ujamaa policies in Tanzania can yield a well-rounded perspective. Both American papers are reputable and offer diverse editorial viewpoints, ensuring coverage of Ujamaa from different angles. Their international focus allows for broader contextual analysis, examining the policies in relation to global implications. *The Daily News* provides essential local insight, capturing the nuances of Ujamaa as experienced by Tanzanians. *The Daily News* is a government-owned prominent English-language newspaper in Tanzania. It has a significant history dating back to the country's early independence era. It was first published on 26 April 1972, but through its predecessors (*The Standard*, which was first published as the *Tanganyika Standard*), it documented Tanzania's post-colonial public affairs and development initiatives. However, one of the criticisms of the paper is that it served as a mouthpiece for the ruling political party, reflecting the socialist policies of President Julius Nyerere's administration. For this reason, as it is a government-owned newspaper, this source was mostly used in this study to provide historical context and a history of official government policies on the Ujamaas. This combination enables a triangulated approach in which American newspapers highlight

dominant global ideological perspectives and criticisms while local newspapers provide regional accounts and viewpoints. Furthermore, analyzing multiple sources promotes critical engagement with the material, allowing for the identification of biases and fostering a more comprehensive understanding. As a result, this approach enhances the analysis, ensuring a balanced exploration of Ujamaa policies and practices rather than hindering them.

Thirdly, in addition to these three newspaper sources, a mixture of policy-relevant documents created during the time period was used in this study. This was a total of ten ($n = 10$) government documents, including six annual reports, two key presidential speeches, and two independent institutional studies covering the period from 1965 to 1985. These policy documents were useful for further comprehending the government's position, challenges, successes, and ideological underpinnings of Ujamaa communities in Tanzania at the time. Again, these ten key policy documents were not a part of the systematic software-assisted content analysis because, usually, software-based analysis is applied to larger volumes (or sample sizes) of documents ($> =100$) [128,129]. The policy documents were primarily for cross-referencing historical data. Given that the newspapers offered rich international public discourse and were the main primary sources needed to achieve the methodological contribution of the study (content analysis), these documents were better suited for grounding and cross-referencing local Ujamaa policy. They offered valuable insights into the official goals, state strategies, and implementation plans that underpinned the Ujamaa communities. Information from the documents, such as the Arusha policy and annual plans, are incorporated throughout the analysis and discussion as they delineate specific policies on land reform, cooperative establishment, and rural development. These were useful for understanding how communal living and self-reliance were meant to be achieved, and thus where Ujamaa fell short, and how it impacted the ecology of the country over time. The newspaper articles for the *New York Times* and *The Washington Post* were accessed through ProQuest Databases. Meanwhile, *The Daily News* articles were accessed through the University of Dar es Salaam online (open access) library repository.

Finally, the mixed methods software NVivo was used to conduct (manage and standardize) the content analysis of historical newspaper sources. This software facilitated the systematic organization, coding, and analysis of textual data, enabling efficient categorization of themes, tracking changes over time in newspaper coverage, and identifying patterns in public discourse concerning Ujamaa and sustainability

ideals. The software selection was based on its availability and capacity to handle substantial volumes of textual data. This was instrumental in elucidating nuanced insights into the implementation and societal impacts of Ujamaa policies. Extensive attention was dedicated to thoroughly preprocessing and validating these data sources. This helped to guarantee meaningful and dependable analysis while also accounting for potential biases or errors introduced during digitization or optical character recognition processes for the files uploaded to the software for analysis.

4. Process, analysis, and results

The content analysis conducted had eight main steps. This fostered a systematic analysis of the newspaper discourse, which uncovered insights into the social realities of the time in terms of the ideas and practices relevant to sustainability and social-environmental transformation in Tanzania between the mid-1960s and mid-1980s. The discourse process is outlined below. Also, see Fig. 1 for the graphical overview of the process. The first step was to define the research questions specific to the content analysis. This involved formulating specific questions to guide the analysis. These guiding questions were: (1) what major themes can be identified in these sources, and how do they relate to each other? (2) how were certain topics framed, or how is language used to construct meanings? With the research questions and scope defined, this was followed by the selection of sources. This involved using keyword searches and date ranges to identify the sample from the online database that housed the policy documents and newspaper articles. Again, these were ProQuest and the University of Dar es Salaam Library digital/online repositories, respectively. Meanwhile, hard copies of policy documents consulted were accessed through Boston University's African Studies Library collections.

The keywords were searched for in three tiers within the date range 1965 to 1985—Tier-1, Tier-2, and Tier-3, each moving toward achieving a final data sample. Note that the study period for the sources consulted is two years earlier than the actual implementation of the Ujamaa, this is to make room for analyzing the policy development discourse leading up to the Arusha Declaration, which established Ujamaa as a formal state policy in 1967. For Tier-1, two keywords, *Ujamaa* and *Julius Nyerere*, were inputted into the consulted online databases. This narrowed the selection of relevant news articles to a collection size ($N = 1937$) of the most relevant sources. This data was then cleaned to remove *repeated newspaper articles*—those news articles that were duplicated in the first

Fig. 1. An outline of the content analysis process.

Table 1
Output data from keyword searches in historical newspaper online databases.

Keyword search information	Number of news articles (frequency)
Search period: January 01, 1965 - December 31, 1985	
Tier-1 keyword search results:	
Keywords:	
a) <i>Ujamaa</i>	127
a) <i>Julius Nyerere</i>	1810
Total number of news articles from initial search	1937
Total number of news articles removed (<i>N</i> = 654)	
■ News articles outside of study period	-280
■ Inconspicuous news articles	-239
■ Repeated news articles	-134
Final sample dataset (<i>N</i>)	1282

batch of search results (Tier-1 search). Also removed were *inconspicuous newspaper articles*. These were articles that, on closer inspection, were not relevant to the substantive topic even though they contained the Tier-1 keywords. *Outside of the study period, articles* that appeared in the Tier-1 keyword search results for whatever reason were also removed as they were produced before or after the historical period under investigation (1965–1985) and likely offered no contextual relevance to the study’s goals. The remaining news articles formed the research sample (*N* = 1282). This systematic sampling ensured that a wide range of different discussions were included and helped to avoid bias in the selection of articles. Table 1 summarizes the results of this first-level analysis that got to the data sample of newspaper sources.

The sample was then formatted into a dataset for analysis. Using NVivo, a word frequency search was performed on the sample dataset (Tier-2 search). The word frequency search quantitatively identified terms that populated the newspaper articles in the sample. From this, key themes can be assumed based on how large or small the frequency of certain words is. Following the word frequency analysis, a selection of keywords and concepts were then coded and categorized based on the research questions and goals. Coding organizes data and identifies pat-

terns in sources that facilitate comparisons across the news articles used in this study [130]. A total of eight (8) high-order codes were arrived at, along with sixteen (16) sub-codes (low-order). Sub-codes help to further contextualize the content being analyzed in the dataset. This is identifying whether the content is affirming the concept or is in opposition to it. For example, *pro-socialist* and *anti-socialist*. Table 2 outlines the eight codes, their sub-codes with their interpretative descriptions, and frequency results.

Following coding and categorization, a Tier-3 keyword search was performed on the sample sources using the eight (high-order) codes. This provided a sub-sample of sorts on how these specific themes (codes) were covered in the news articles over the study period. Each term is categorized based on its typical connotation in discussions related to socioeconomic development, ecology, sustainability, and the environment per the research goals and theoretical approach. Some of the codes are combined because of their direct contextual relations to each other from the systematic word frequency search performed in NVivo. For example, *farm* and *land* were combined as each term was often found used together in the same articles. Another example is combining *sustainable*, *self-sufficient*, and *self-reliance* because they were found to be used in a similar ideological sense in some news articles. The concept of self-reliance was also used interchangeably with self-sufficiency, which, in the context of how they were used in the sources, was to be achieved through conservation, farming innovation, careful resource use, and so on. These concepts are directly related to the principles of sustainability. So, although the word sustainable or sustainability was seldom used during the time period under study, other terms, such as *self-reliance* and *self-sufficiency*, can be taken to convey similar precepts, meanings, and intentions that are associated with the literature on sustainability. For example, see works such as [131–133].

Following the quantitative code-based or summative analysis, the dataset was ready for more substantive analysis and interpretation (relational analysis). This is where the content of the newspaper articles was analyzed based on their positive or negative disposition to each of the codes (concepts) and the meanings they conveyed. This involved manually reviewing the text in each document (around each code) and assigning context. Through this step, the dominant discourses, ideological positions, and shifts over time on the purpose of the Ujamaa communities and their relevance to ecological shifts and sustainability

Table 2
Coding, categorization, and frequency (f) results.

Capitalism (f =85)	Socialism (f=156)	Ecology/Environment (f =267)	Sustainability (f = 39)
<i>Anti-capitalism</i> : a dissatisfaction and critique of capitalist market-driven economic systems. The affinity or preference for cooperative and egalitarian models of socioeconomic systems.	<i>Anti-socialism</i> : the dissatisfaction and critique of socialist economic systems. Reluctance to implement cooperative and egalitarian models of socioeconomic governance.	<i>Ecological balance</i> : engaging in practices or policies that maintain or enhances equilibrium in human-natural ecosystem. Preservation and conservation of natural resources.	<i>Pro-sustainability</i> : support for sustainable practices. The focus on renewable efficient use and protection of resources for future generations. Emphasizes self-sufficiency and self-reliance but acknowledges interdependency.
<i>Pro-capitalism</i> : the support for capitalist market-driven economic systems. The preference and prioritization of market and business (or elitist) over cooperative and egalitarian models of socioeconomic systems.	<i>Pro-socialism</i> : the support for socialist economic systems. Favored implementation of cooperative and egalitarian models of socioeconomic governance.	<i>Ecological disruption</i> : engaging in practices or policies that create imbalance or disturbance in human-natural ecosystems. Unsustainable use of natural resources.	<i>Unsustainable practices</i> : practices that are harmful to the environment and society. The depletion of natural resources and unhealthy dependence on fossil fuels and extractive industries.
Development (f = 215)	Colonialism (f = 45)	Rural (f = 47)	Urban/City (f = 30)
<i>Sustainable Development</i> : an organized collaborative socioeconomic growth that prioritizes community and sustainability.	<i>Decolonization</i> : a continued focus on deconstructing colonial rule and colonial practices. The focus on self-determination principles.	<i>Rural decay</i> : socioeconomic vulnerability is amplified in rural areas. The removal or limiting resources available to rural populations.	<i>Urban planning</i> : a focus on urban planning and organized development of urban areas.
<i>Market-oriented development</i> : a focus on profit-driven development with private ownership.	<i>Neocolonialism</i> : a tendency to revert to indirect colonial control or colonial influence in decision-making.	<i>Rural development</i> : the improvement of rural infrastructure and quality of life.	<i>Urban apathy</i> : the disinterest in or lack of engagement in urban communities. The removal or limiting of resources available to urban population.

Fig. 3. A concept map of the main findings.

could be identified. It also included deriving meanings and societal implications embedded in the texts (discourse). The findings from the analysis and their interpretations were then compared and contextualized. This primarily entailed cross-referencing the historical news articles’ content with policy documents, where the findings were further situated within broader historical, social, and political events to understand their impact and relevance. This step was followed by reflecting on the findings in a manner that considered alternative interpretations. The final step was writing up and reporting the findings, which are included in the subsequent findings and discussion section.

Fig. 2 outlines a cluster of results and data visualizations from this Tier-3 code analysis. This includes results of the code frequencies, word trees, and a word cloud. The word trees show the variety of newspaper articles where the code words are found and the contexts in which they are used in the news articles. Meanwhile, the word cloud shows the main words and themes in the sample sources. In this regard, *economic development*, *socialism*, and *capital* were the three highest-frequency words found. Meanwhile, *land* is the most frequent ecological or environment-related word found within the dataset. Concerning the root word “Capital” identified in the dataset, the newspaper articles included in the analysis were those that were directly about capitalist ideology/economic systems. In terms of yearly distribution of sources, 1977 and 1979 were the years of the highest media and public discourse about the

Ujamaa ideology and communities in the sample. This makes sense. These two years are among the peak years of Ujamaa implementation, as well as public discontent with the policy. The frequency of these keywords demonstrates ideology’s role and impact in shaping public, media, and government discourse regarding the implementation of the Ujamaas.

5. Findings and discussion

The two main lessons for green transitions derived through this study are (1) the profound impact of ideology on effectively implementing (or impeding) sustainability programs and projects in resource-dependent developing countries. This includes public, government, and international responses to alternative ideology in terms of support/compliance or pushback against it. And (2) the value of re-designing social systems by integrating ecological principles and social equity in a way that leverages local knowledge and builds ecological resilience into socio-economic development planning. Fig. 3 summarizes the main findings of this study. These findings provide insights for optimizing green transitions (low-carbon or social-environmental) in post-colonial societies or Global South developing countries. Additionally, they offer key areas for consideration in the ongoing global green transition process.

Fig. 4. Physical layout of a typical Ujamaa community.

5.1. Government-led green transitions

Governments have historically been responsible for the natural environment of a country. Large-scale social, economic, or ecological transformations often rely on government policies to facilitate and sustain these transitions. These can have varied outcomes—for better or worse [134,135]. For instance, the expansion of the American Midwest, particularly from the 1820s to the late 1800s, was greatly influenced by government initiatives such as the Homestead Act of 1862 [136]. This act encouraged settlement and agricultural development, transforming large areas into farmlands [137,138]. However, this rapid transformation often overlooked Indigenous rights and the importance of ecological integrity, resulting in habitat destruction, loss of biodiversity, and annihilation of indigenous populations and societies that inhabited those lands [139,140].

Another notable example is China's Great Leap Forward, which began in 1958. This campaign aimed to quickly industrialize the country and collectivize agriculture [141]. However, it resulted in severe ecological disruption, widespread deforestation, and famine due to unsustainable practices [142]. In contrast, China's Great Transition began in the late 20th century and accelerated in the 2000s, driven by a commitment to a more sustainable approach [143]. Key policies, such as the 2005 Renewable Energy Law and subsequent Five-Year Plans focused on green development, have since established China as a global leader in renewable energy capacity by 2020 [144]. Notwithstanding current and potential future challenges, these developments highlight the importance of effective policy design in ecological transitions. They also shed light on the idea of authoritative central planning and its often adverse impacts on ecological change in the context of communist and socialist-leaning societies [145,146], as Tanzania was at beginning of the Ujamaa experiment. In more contemporary contexts, the European Union's Green Deal, launched in 2019, aims to make Europe climate-neutral by 2050. It emphasizes sustainable practices across various sectors, connecting economic growth with environmental responsibility [147]. This includes policies that support sustainable agriculture, biodiversity restoration, and the transition to circular

economies [148].

Therefore, government-led green transitions often aim to balance environmental sustainability with economic development and social equity (or justice), especially in least developed countries (LDCs) that are still working to achieve several basic socioeconomic development markers, such as access to clean drinking water, universal healthcare, and food security [149,150]. In Tanzania, the Ujamaa policy framework, introduced in the 1960s by Julius Nyerere, serves as a historical case study for understanding these transitions. The Ujamaa case also demonstrates the practice where government-led green initiatives may co-opt traditional or local values, practices, and principles and try to scale them up to a national level. For instance, principles of community involvement and collective action, were part of the long-held Tanzanian cultural belief in Ujamaa philosophy.

However, government co-optation sometimes does not work well. Scholars note that co-optation often happens when a dominant power incorporates or adopts ideas or movements to suppress dissent and maintain control [151–153]. As a result, local communities often perceive the national green or sustainability transitions with skepticism, feeling that their voices may not be adequately considered. While these contemporary efforts are presented as pathways to environmental sustainability and climate resilience, it's important to ensure true community involvement. These dynamics highlight the past tensions between the ideals of Ujamaa and contemporary governance practices. While green transitions can align with principles of social equity and communal welfare, it is essential to critically examine whether they genuinely involve local stakeholders or merely serve as instruments of co-optation.

Contemporarily, the Tanzanian government is implementing various green initiatives, including reforestation projects, sustainable agricultural practices, and renewable energy programs. For example, the National Afforestation Program and the Trillion Trees Project aim to engage communities in reforestation efforts [154,155]. However, there is a risk that these programs may overlook genuine local participation [156]. Instead of empowering communities, they could reinforce governmental authority by extracting resources without meaningful

community awareness and engagement [157].

Reflecting on Ujamaa's legacy, effective green transitions in Tanzania would best prioritize community-led initiatives, ensuring that local voices drive future green transition policies. Through fostering authentic community-based participation, the government could align its green transition goals with the original spirit of Ujamaa and the global green movement to promote resilience, equity, and a carbon-neutral future in the face of unfolding environmental challenges.

5.2. Impact of political and social ideologies on green transitions

While socialism was a needed force for solidarity against the vestiges of colonialism in newly independent Tanzania, given the internal and external dominance of liberal capitalism, it may not have been the most realistic model for the country's long-term socioeconomic growth and development. Before the formation of Tanzania, Tanganyika, the large mainland area which constitutes about 99 % of the country, was a colony. It was first part of German East Africa from the 1880s to 1919. Then, the League of Nations placed it under British administration. And in 1947, Tanganyika became a United Nations Trust Territory, a status it kept until its independence in 1964. Meanwhile, the neighboring Zanzibar was a renowned trading hub, successively controlled by the Portuguese, the Sultanate of Oman, and was then a British protectorate by the end of the nineteenth century. Under colonial rule, there was violence, large-scale deposition of native land, labor exploitation, and extensive resource extraction from these ecologies for the benefit of European empires [158]. In this regard, colonization is thought to have harmed Tanzania's ecology and arrested its socioeconomic progress, similar to other African nations [159,160].

Upon the acquisition of political independence, Nyerere and the other architects of the newly independent Tanzania saw socialism as a way of righting the wrongs of the past. Ideology, therefore, plays a vital role in social and environmental movements [161,162]. Ideologies provide the values, belief systems, and guidelines for creating alternative ecological realities [163]. Although not often recognized as such, decolonization was an attempt to undo imperial policies that were harmful to Africa's natural environment. As Ross [164] observed, "the fact that colonial rule lasted barely seventy years [in Africa] makes the environmental impact of imperial conquest appear less decisive than is often assumed" (p.11). With European decolonization underway across the continent during the 1960s and 1970s, socialism was viewed as the antithesis of colonialism by the newly independent nation-states. For Tanzania, socialism informed the core tenets of the Ujamaa policy and communities. Meaning "familyhood" or "extended family" in Swahili, Ujamaa was the Africanization of socialist principles, which were considered inherent to traditional African values of community and cooperation. Emphasizing cooperation and solidarity among citizens, African socialism provided the values that would empower workers and marginalized groups while challenging capitalist exploitation that had come to define European imperialism and conquests. Ujamaa communities were established as a way to practically embody these principles within the larger national transformations in Tanzania following independence. David Ottaway, writing for the Washington Post, recounted: "[o]n a continent increasingly inclined toward socialism, Tanzania's communal Ujamaa villages have long been regarded as a kind of bellwether and testing ground for African socialist theories." These communities were, in essence, -the practice-of specific political, economic, cultural, and ecological ideologies held by Tanzania's top decision-makers—the political elite.

5.2.1. Sustainability, socialism, and ecological change

Although not often recognized as such, many of the African socialist principles that informed Ujamaa communities have conceptual and ideological overlaps with sustainability. Both socialism and sustainability have core philosophies of self-reliance and self-sufficiency. Organized around common values, Ujamaa villages sought to find

natural, renewable, and long-term (sustainable) alternatives to food production, energy, water, transportation, and waste management systems, as well as the larger social systems that support them [165]. In a speech to conference delegates of the ruling Tanganyika African National Union (TANU) party, Nyerere clarified what self-reliance means as articulated in the 1967 Arusha Declaration. His explanation underlines the connection between Ujamaa, African socialism, and sustainability principles. For Nyerere, self-reliance meant "that we must make maximum use of the resources which we have ...[b]ut our real emphasis will be on using the skills that we already have and developing the resources that we now possess...we [also] have to modernize our farming if we are to improve our standard of living" [166], p. 1–3). Essentially, a nation cannot be fully self-reliant without being sustainable. This form of self-reliant sustainability was to be achieved on a national scale. However, it was part of a continent-wide effort to once and for all decouple from larger socioeconomic forces, which for centuries fostered the dependency of tropical regions on Western colonial powers.

Ujamaa, therefore, inadvertently attempted to restore (and transform) the landscape ecology of Tanzania—demonstrating the potent impact of politics on ecological change in post-colonial Africa. In addition to self-reliance, at the core of these two paradigms—socialism and sustainability—is egalitarianism. Socialism aims to diminish economic inequality by facilitating equitable access to resources and opportunities. This includes the recognition that equal access to land is directly associated with collective empowerment [167]. Similarly, sustainability strives to attain environmental and social equity. It calls upon governments to ensure that people have access to clean air, water, and other resources essential for survival [168]. European colonization had displaced Tanzania's indigenous land practices that harmonized with nature. The capitalist pursuit of profit resulted in environmental degradation and unequal resource distribution for centuries across the landscape and wider African region. According to Nyerere, "[i]n traditional African life...people were equal [and] co-operated together... In traditional African famil[ies]...the land was "ours" the crops were "ours"... Ujamaa villages use local resources and traditional knowledge" [166], p. 18–19). Therefore, aiming to transform rural communities, Ujamaa promoted collective farming and social cohesion, blending socialist principles with Indigenous practices to mitigate ecological degradation caused by previous colonial and capitalist practices.

Furthermore, both socialism and sustainability prioritize long-term development planning over short-term economic gains—an aversion to the capitalist logic of profit maximization. Sustainability focuses on enacting policies that reduce adverse environmental and social impacts on future generations [26]. Likewise, socialism legitimized government intervention in the Tanzanian economy to provide essential services to ensure longevity [38]. In Ujamaa communities, this included healthcare and education services, as well as agricultural supplies of Ujamaa programs. However, there were disproportional challenges between the rural-urban development dichotomy under Ujamaa. While underscoring the model egalitarian nature of Ujamaa, New York Times reporter Michael Kaufman [169] pointed out that the "[Chamwino] co-operative village ... and [other rural cooperatives] like it, sustain the vision of a socialist, egalitarian and self-sufficient Tanzania." Inadvertently, in his report, Kaufman showcased the dual blow of Ujamaa on rural-urban social ecologies when he cited "reports of shortages and unemployment in the cities." So, while Ujamaa bloomed in the early phases of implementation, it was shifting development from cities, worsening conditions in the nation's emerging urban centers. Furthermore, Chamwino was one of the model communities that received more government resources than usual. Based on the news report, it was doing well at the time, but Chamwino was not the norm as other communities struggled.

5.2.2. Liberal-capitalist anxiety

There is a more sinister side to the role (or side effect) of ideologies in

green transitions. That is, alternative ideologies are often ruthlessly criticized and sabotaged by proponents of the pre-existing dominant ideology—especially if they are perceived as not beneficial to already powerful interest groups. Here, the Marxian critiques of socialist state-sanctioned resource reallocation and capitalist resource accumulation by dispossession emerge [170–172]. Socialism and sustainability, in some ways, are fundamentally opposed to capitalist logic, where production and allocation decisions are largely determined by market forces and the supply and demand interactions among producers and consumers [173]. At least, in the Ujamaa case, the capitalist logic was a colonial by-product that was not to be replicated in the newly independent nation. Nyerere lamented that “Ujamaa ... describes [African] socialism. It opposes capitalism, which seeks to build a happy society based on... exploitation ...” [174]. As such, the prevailing capitalist-liberal domestic and international atmosphere was not particularly compatible with the egalitarian ideals that Ujamaa communities were to represent. Tanzania’s attempt to transition from colonial capitalism to socialism thus created tensions both domestically and internationally.

So too, will transitioning to green economies and sustainable societies create or unmask deep ideological tensions in African societies. At the local level, there was certainly discontentment with Ujamaa. However, the initial angst seemed slightly lowered because Ujamaa was being implemented as part of the process of creating a new country. It was grounded in traditionalism and nationalism, which bolstered its appeal to the anti-colonial sentiments held by the masses at that time. Romanticisms of nationalism and nationhood were high—a sort of post-colonial euphoria. This no doubt inspired the local polity to go along with the program. Howe [175], writing for the *New York Times*, captured this early mass compliance when the leader of Kerege Village remarked: “[w]e have too many people here, [e]verybody wants to join the ujamaas” (p. 5). But around four years into the project, the independence jubilation wore off. Significant factions of Tanzanian society, both the villagers and the business class, became disgruntled with the socialist planned economic model that was being championed by Nyerere. It was what *New York Times* reporter Charles Mohr [176] described as a “Leftist Urgency” that came over the Nyerere Administration, with the seizure of industry and local businesses, and commercial properties that affected mostly the “middle-class” and “Asian, Indian, and Pakistani” communities living in Tanzania at the time. Concerns escalated as state intervention and regulation were thought to stifle entrepreneurship and innovation, leading to economic stagnation or inefficiency. The business class’s reaction is typical, in some cases exaggerated, and in others somewhat justified. Capitalist anxiety often manifests as fear of losing personal wealth, economic freedoms, market-driven incentives under socialist or communist systems, or general fear of proletarian revolutions [177,178]. For some, that fear was becoming real in the 1970s Tanzania.

Meanwhile, at the international level, although intellectually advocating cross-cutting liberal values, such as democracy and freedom, the overarching international perception of what was transpiring in post-colonial Tanzania was rooted in the fear of communism and anti-liberalism [179]. As a result, Ujamaa communities experienced heightened criticism because they were aligned with socialist thought, which was (and is) often considered a derivative of (or precursor to) communism and even fascism. These were, after all, ideologies that were thought to have brought the perils of modern global warfare to the West. Cold War tensions and propaganda perpetuated negative perceptions of socialism and communism in capitalist societies (or liberal democracies). The Soviet Union’s villainous archetype was so palpable among the United States-led Northern bloc at that time. An intriguing example of this international ideological antagonism was captured by *New York Times* staff writer Edward’s Burks’ [180] piece on Lady Marion Chesham, a member of Tanzania’s social and political high society and US native turned Tanzania citizen. Lady Marion had traveled to the United States from Tanzania to explain Ujamaa to dignitaries

there. Her core argument was “that Tanzania ... is not leaning to the Communist block and is not anti-American despite some misunderstandings.” Besides seeking some “no strings attached to aid,” she went to set the record straight as “Tanzania seems to have got the reputation through some American press accounts of being Communist.”

Ujamaa communities (as an alternative model of development) were essentially being undertaken in a world that was dominated by liberal-capitalist hegemony and an emerging global ideological divide between communism and liberalism. It seemed destined to fail. Furthermore, by 1980, at the regional or sub-regional level, member countries of the East African Cooperation (EAC), of which Tanzania was a part, were dissuaded by international media reports and testimonials from embarking on the widespread replication or implementation of Ujamaa sustainable communities. This was also likely the result of the Uganda-Tanzania War (1978–1979) and the collapse of the EAC around a year before the war outbreak [181,182].

5.3. The Practice: designing and engineering green-sustainable systems

Another strong theme that emerged from the Ujamaa case study is that social-environmental transitions are not arbitrary, they require structures and processes to support them. Restructuring, re-designing, or re-engineering social-environmental systems, therefore, becomes an essential part of effectively moving from ideology to practice. Nyerere recognized this and attempted to do so through socialism. However—again—the socialist approach was not fully contextualized in the liberal capitalist realities of the time. For nearly every newly independent African nation, this was a challenge [183,184]. With the green sustainability movement gaining ground, adopting an ecosystem approach in designing sustainability projects could perhaps prove useful for the present and future green transitions in African countries. Ujamaa communities attempted to pool resources and minimize negative impacts on the natural environment by becoming more socially, culturally, economically, and ecologically sustainable. Through the principles of self-reliance, Ujamaa villages were essentially attempting to be self-sustaining ecosystems.

Maintaining ecological balance is crucial when implementing and maintaining sustainability projects, whether they are considered alternative, innovative, or new [185]. That is, paying close attention to the fundamental components of that system and how they work together for the benefit of the community (or country) in question [186]. This involves identifying essential needs such as food, energy, water, and shelter, and then developing solutions to meet these needs locally and externally if need be [187]. The systems or areas for green transformation in Africa are agriculture and food systems, infrastructure, technology, energy, education and skills, the economy, and ecological resilience [188,189]. Although not exactly in contemporary terms, Ujamaa communities tried to incorporate these components into their designs to varying degrees [39], but had varying outcomes. These outcomes irregularities were largely due to insufficient resources, ideological determinism, and governance challenges. One significantly missing component of this ideology to practice transition was a greater commitment to resilience and interdependence, which are core logics of functioning ecosystems.

5.3.1. Agriculture and food systems

Ujamaa communities and policies focused on agriculture. This was a step in the right direction, as agriculture was the main industry depended upon by the majority of Tanzania’s population for livelihood and subsistence. Green and sustainable transitions, if they are to be just, equitable, and cater to the needs of the masses or most vulnerable, are most positively impactful when they prioritize industries or sectors (or access to resources) connected to the livelihoods or subsistence of those people—marginalized identities, the poor, displaced, the geographically remote or peripheral, and others [190–192]. Collective rural agriculture was considered a viable solution by Nyerere’s government. It

emphasized rural development through cooperative farming and 'village-level' industries [39]. Communities were encouraged to produce their own food and goods to reduce national dependency on external markets. Farmers were also encouraged to adopt high-yielding staple varieties of crops, such as maize and cassava [19]. To supplement their efforts, the government provided support in the form of fertilizer and infrastructure, such as roads and irrigation systems [40]. About 97 % of Tanzania is still dependent on agriculture, and for >80 % of Tanzanians today, food security remains a major issue [193,194]. This trend is indicative of the wider continent. Over 70 % of Africa is dependent on agriculture [195].

There is often a tendency for contemporary green transition initiatives or sustainability projects to be preoccupied with industries that are high-yield but only benefit a small segment of wealthy people, such as energy [196]. However, as green transitions take shape in natural resource-dependent developing countries, it is necessary to prioritize agriculture through organic farming practices and make agricultural and food systems more sustainable. Based on the unique environmental features of Tanzania and socio-ecological gaps in similar developing African countries, this will be best served by focusing on the following three key areas. First, the green transition will need to regenerate soil health, conserve water, and sequester carbon [197]. Secondly, it must focus on waste reduction and recycling initiatives to minimize resource consumption and pollution [198]. Thirdly, there must be an emphasis on ecological restoration efforts to repair degraded, over-extracted landscapes and enhance biodiversity [199].

5.3.2. Green technology, infrastructure, and clean energy

Ujamaa policies also promoted the use of modern farming techniques and tools [39]. The agricultural sector had to increase efficiency and productivity to meet the growing internal demands while reducing dependence on external markets. Gradual mechanization of farming and the construction of better facilities to accommodate light agro-manufacturing began to take shape during the 1970s [200]. These technological innovations were introduced to the rural population, which constituted about 95 % of Tanzania at the time [201]. This was a step in the right direction, given that technological innovation is shown to be a major contributor to jump-starting economic progress and is widely considered a precursor for future green economic growth [202, 203]. However, the problem with technology innovation under Ujamaa was that there was limited extension to adjacent sectors [204]. Throughout Ujamaa's implementation, transportation networks declined drastically due to neglect. Meanwhile, due to socialist policies, capitalist activities such as industry, banking, and even small and medium enterprises were adversely impacted [205]. Ironically, in the years that followed, despite the self-reliance mantra, Tanzania became even more reliant on international aid [206].

Further drawing upon the lessons of Ujamaa, future green transitions in Africa will require a smart ecological design that centers on technological innovation in agriculture. This is because most contemporary African societies are still culturally and economically based on the agricultural sector, and some have strong communal philosophies [207]. It does not suggest that maintaining or promoting communal living is necessary to make efficient green transitions in Africa. Nonetheless, from the infrastructural design standpoint, green transitions will involve retrofitting existing industrial buildings and housing stock with energy-efficient technologies. As well as promoting sustainable design principles in new construction projects to reduce environmental impact and improve health and safety [208]. A benefit thought to have been derived from Ujamaa communal design and living arrangements was that it contributed to addressing the problem of "tribalization," which was a prevalent issue at the time in many newly independent African nations. Tribalization strongly segmented Tanzania's populations along ancestral tribal lines. However, under Ujamaa, people from different tribal and ethnic backgrounds lived together, uniting Tanzanians across ethnic lines [209]. Thereby significantly reducing ethnic conflicts.

Certainly, there were instances of tension, but for the most part, Tanzania remained largely untouched by the tribal and political tensions that affected several other African countries in the immediate post-independence (post-colonial) era of the 1960s and 70 s [209,210].

Ujamaa shows that there must also be a simultaneously strong emphasis on agricultural and adjacent sectors to maintain sustainability initiatives. Thus, present and future investments in agriculture are best when matched with significant levels of investments in the transportation and energy sectors. At the heart of this global green movement is the recognition that continued reliance on fossil fuels is unsustainable and poses grave risks to planet Earth and its inhabitants [211]. Transitioning to carbon-neutral sustainable societies has thus become a significant indicator of global modernity. Renewable energy technologies such as solar, wind, and hydropower can provide clean, decentralized sources of electricity, help reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and help mitigate climate change by reducing the volume of carbon emissions released into the atmosphere [212]. This also includes accelerating research and development in clean technologies such as carbon capture and storage, advanced nuclear reactors, and green hydrogen production [213].

However, green or clean energy (renewables and low-carbon emitting) transition will pose a challenge for African countries. This is because of ecological paradoxes underway in Africa. While the majority of the continent consists of developing countries that are highly susceptible to the effects of climate change, there are also African oil-producing nations that make significant contributions to carbon emissions, especially those within the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC)—Algeria, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Libya, Nigeria, and the Congo Republic [214]. Meanwhile, other African countries have abundant oil reserves and rely heavily on fossil fuel extraction and exports as a main source of revenue for socioeconomic development [215]. OPEC's African member nations that produce oil encounter extra obstacles due to market dynamics, geopolitical pressures, and economic vulnerabilities linked to changes in oil prices. Consequently, African countries are dealing with the dual challenges of underestimating and adapting to climate change, all while contending with the economic and political repercussions of their reliance on extracting and exporting fossil fuels [214,216]. As resource-dependent societies, it will become increasingly imperative for African governments and industries to consider various significant issues related to social equity in clean energy and green technology [217]. Furthermore, over time, especially from a political ecology perspective, there will be a need for greater attention to matters such as community-owned renewable energy projects and the promotion of energy justice to mitigate energy inequality as needed [218].

5.3.3. Green skills, education, and social equity

As green transitions unfold in Tanzania and wider Africa, there will be a focus on creating green employment and training programs. Ujamaa policies—again—advocated for social equality, education, and skills training but overlooked some of the nuances of changing social and economic life in Tanzania. As Tanzania's new administration took shape following political independence, there was certainly a concerted effort to organize the society and economy in a way that prioritized social welfare over individual profit [174]. Ujamaa social equity principles, as articulated in the Arusha Declaration, were emphasized through education and training in agricultural practices to improve productivity [39]. These initiatives were usually offered through the prism of traditional ideals of how families operated, but in many cases, they were no longer applicable [87,219]. Nevertheless, education improvement was one of the lasting solid legacies of the Ujamaa years, including a much higher pre-colonial literacy rate and halving infant mortality through access to medical facilities and increased health awareness [220].

Ujamaa policies also aimed to uplift marginalized communities. Informed by socialist ideals, the founding government of Tanzania wanted to create a more just society where everyone had access to basic

needs and opportunities, regardless of their socioeconomic background [166]. This involved advocating for government intervention in the economy to guarantee essential services like healthcare, education, and housing. Yet, by the 1970s, the people who were predominantly uprooted from their urban or peri-urban life and moved to rural villages were often those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds and they were not members of the political elite. For example, The Washington Post reported on an article that appeared in a local Swedish magazine on the eve of Nyerere's official visit to the country. The Washington Post article stated that an official from the Swedish International Development Agency wrote that the Nyerere administration's recent effort to relocate "6 million peasants" to the planned Ujamaa villages was a show of "cruelty and abuse of power by the country's authorities ... [and that] the Tanzanian army had begun to destroy homes and crops of villagers who refused to obey government orders to leave [their homes and relocate to the planned villages]" (p. 20). Ultimately, due to local pushback and international criticism, the Tanzanian administration's forced relocation efforts failed. And toward the early 1980s, there was mass withdrawal from subsistence and commercial agriculture and rural communal life in general [221]. Meanwhile, the people still living in urban areas remained in the cities and seemingly practiced much smaller-scale urban farming [204]. Today, Tanzania is one of Africa's most populous nations, with a total population of over 67,400,000 people [222]. The population is youthful and rapidly growing, with about 60 % of the population being under age 25 [223]. This means a potentially strong workforce, but also additional investments in education, health, and employment will be needed in the coming years [224]. Future green transitions will, therefore, need to consider all these factors while recognizing this urban-rural dichotomy, as well as potentially changing cultural values about livelihoods.

5.3.4. Rural-urban ecologies for community-based resilience

Whereas Ujamaa focused on the development and investments in primarily rural landscapes, green transitions will need to focus on resource allocations and empowerment that benefit both rural and urban communities. Ujamaa transformed the ecology of Tanzania. It was an attempt at rural development towards the overarching goal of national economic development. Throughout the implementation of the national development policy, thousands of Ujamaa villages were established in rural areas, and millions of people relocated [40]. It was predicated on the idea of collective agriculture through the "villagization" of the countryside [39]. Nyerere argued that European colonialism had caused urbanization, which was driven by wage labor and had disrupted the traditional pre-colonial rural African society [174]. He believed that his government could recreate precolonial traditions in Tanzania and re-establish a traditional level of mutual respect, thus returning the people to settled, moral ways of life [200]. The primary way to achieve this goal, according to Nyerere, was to relocate people from urban cities like the capital, Dar es Salaam, to newly created villages in the rural countryside [174]. Initially, the process started slowly and was voluntary, with only around 800 collective settlements in place by the end of the 1960s, and by the end of the 1970s, there were over 2500 of these villages in Tanzania [225].

The Tanzanian administration had begun to force people to leave the cities and move to the rural collective villages. Both the local polity and international perception of Ujamaa began to shift from optimism to pessimism as Nyerere's reign was thought to have become more oppressive by the mid to late 70s. In a special report, Africa-correspondent for The Washington Post, David Ottaway [226] recounts that "[o]verzealous party officials have resorted to the use of force ... bulldozing down mud and stick houses or rounding up rural villagers" to move them into the planned Ujamaa communities. Moreover, the villages were far from sufficient (p. 37). Furthermore, during an economic recession, wars, and tribal and guerilla militants' dominance of rural areas, foreign aid into Tanzania had skyrocketed [226]. This further raised criticism of the Nyerere self-reliant agenda that was

to have been achieved through Ujamaa.

Interestingly, much of this emphasis on rural development still has significant sway in development policy discourse and practice in Tanzania and across Africa [227]. However, considering the historical analysis of Ujamaa, the findings suggest that for green movements to be effective in Africa, there must be simultaneous engagement with the landscape dialectic of urban renewal and rural development. This includes the interconnections between them, as rural and urban spaces in developing African countries are often drastically different but have shared needs such as water, housing, and economic substance [228, 229]. With its population projected to double by 2050, Africa is also experiencing rapid urbanization and sub-national demographic shifts [230]. For instance, The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [231] and the Sahel and West Africa Club Secretariat (2020) reports that "Africa has the fastest urban growth in the world. The continent's population is projected to double between now and 2050. Two-thirds of this growth will be absorbed by urban areas and, in the next 30 years, cities will be home to an additional 950 million people" (p. 4). This growth brings as many challenges as it does opportunities, including informal settlements and ecological hazards [232]. Those governing green transitions will, therefore, need to pay even closer attention to bottom-up approaches that integrate local ecological knowledge systems in order to prioritize local needs while placing a heavy emphasis on resource (or green investment) matching before pursuing goals or expected sustainability outcomes.

This urban-rural duality calls for greater emphasis on community-based ecological resilience. For example, the series of droughts and famines that ravaged Eastern Africa during the late 1970s and 1980s only added to Tanzania's development burdens. As drought conditions worsened in the 1980s, The New York Times [233] reported that Nyerere lamented the dire weather conditions, saying that "... the East African drought has pushed Tanzania to the brink of "a serious famine," but he does not know where his impoverished Government will get the money to feed the millions who may face starvation." These environmental forces are still threatening East Africa's regional ecosystems today [234]. With increased media attention and evidence of climate change's adverse impact on local food and natural systems, there has been growing recognition in contemporary development policy that sustainability hinges on community socio-ecological resilience [235, 236]. That is the capability or capacity to withstand and bounce back from the adverse impacts of climate and ecological changes (new and old) that are underway across the continent [235,237].

Additionally, there must be a recognition that community resilience in Africa might look similar or different from other regions. Certainly, within the broader Global South, there are overlaps across socio-ecological challenges and needs [238]. Firstly, in addition to increasingly arid conditions, and given the land damage due to extensive mineral resource extraction by colonial and imperial powers, effective green transitions in African countries are best when they entail the restoration of vegetation cover [239,240]. Secondly, there is a need for soil fertility restoration for lands degraded during large-scale monocropping agriculture practiced during colonial administrations [241, 242]. Thirdly, the top-down models of government-led green transitions that Ujamaa represents may prove problematic. To counter this, community-based ecological resilience is useful in its emphasis on food and water security—issues that are greatly impacting Tanzania and East Africa, as they did during the time of Ujamaa in the 1960s to 1980s. Additionally, these grassroots community-based ideologies and practices can contribute to adaptability to socio-ecological challenges but have often proved difficult to scale up. Any contemporary approach to green transitions and sustainable development will increasingly need to grapple with these nuances of development if they intend to be just and prioritize or maximize the benefits of traditional knowledge or Indigenous practices to ecological integrity [243].

With all these considered, as Ruiz-Mallén and Corbera [244] noted, community-based ecological resilience, if applied correctly, has the

potential to harness local knowledge, promote collaboration, and establish sustainable practices that both enhance the natural environment and community well-being. Especially given that such types of government-led top-down (and co-optative) transitions historically, without a deep level of commitment to practicality and community engagement beyond the grassroots inclusion rhetoric and misappropriation, have been prone to failure [245–247]. The complexities of green transitions in developing nations across the African continent and the wider Global South present a smorgasbord of paradoxes, experimentation, and strategic decision-making. However, by all accounts, this could be realized through deep pragmatism and strategically aligning local realities with global benchmarks—forging a delicate balance in the interests of the people, ecological wellbeing, and global sustainable development.

6. Conclusion

The relationship between nature and society has consistently connected socioeconomic development with environmental changes across various temporalities, landscapes, and geographies. Transitioning to carbon-neutral sustainable societies is gradually becoming the *tour de force* or hallmark of postmodernity. However, realizing this greener future seems to encounter greater hurdles in societies marred by a complicated colonial past yet still enmeshed in a neoliberal world order pegged to fossil fuels. As Africa, like the rest of the world, grapples with pressing climate and ecological challenges, the historical case of Tanzania's Ujamaa communities provides insights into the complexities of green transitions and sustainability. The Ujamaa communities were established as part of an alternative development model or experiment in Tanzania between 1967 and 1985. In this analysis, Ujamaa is regarded as one of Africa's first post-colonial attempts at implementing an alternative development model that had underlying sustainability principles. Much like contemporary sustainability communities or ecovillages, Ujamaas presented a vision for society that prioritizes environmental stewardship, community resilience, and social equity.

However, the socialist ideals, which the Ujamaas were to reflect, conflicted with dominant ideological and practical systems. These systems were remnants of colonial interests locally in Tanzania and a liberal-capitalist hegemony at the international level. These ideals also clashed with traditionalist and modernist ideals domestically within Tanzania. As a result, Ujamaa communities were viewed with suspicion, fearing that they represented attempts to subvert mainstream capitalist systems or promote anti-globalist sentiments, ideological alignment, and retreatism. In addition to the ecological challenges of drought, war, famine, and economic collapse in the East African region at the time, Ujamaa faced serious hurdles. The ideology, policy, and practice mostly ended in 1985 when its founder, Julius Nyerere, stepped down from the presidency. Decades later, there are still mixed reviews about the level of success Ujamaa achieved. Nonetheless, through understanding these perceived failures and successes of Ujamaa, primarily through a political ecology lens, present and future decision-makers may adopt more nuanced, realistic, and socio-ecological approaches to green transitions. Or, at the very least, grapple more deeply with the inherent realities and complexities involved in green and sustainability transitioning for societies that are deeply natural resource-dependent while trying to meet the basic socioeconomic development needs of the majority of their population. This approach aligns with global sustainability agendas but also responds to historical legacies and local realities.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Christopher C. Graham: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/hxvvdnz4pd/1>.

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